

Pathways from Contractual Duty to Patent Entitlement: The Law on Employee Inventions in Cameroon

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Abstract:

This article examines the intricate legal dynamics of employee inventions in Cameroon. Under Annex I of the *Organisation Africaine de la Propriété Intellectuelle* patent regime, patent rights generally belong to employers when inventions are made during employment or with employer resources. This rule applies unless a contract provides otherwise. However, uncertainties remain regarding inventors' rights and entitlement to compensation. The crux of the matter arises from ambiguous legal and contractual standards for defining employee inventions, attributing ownership, and ensuring fair remuneration, which undermines innovation incentives and generate disputes under both patent and labour law frameworks. The research question asks to what extent Cameroon's patent and labour laws effectively protect employee inventors and balance employer entitlement with inventor remuneration and legal certainty. The hypothesis is that, although patent rights are contractually vested in employers, the existing regime inadequately protects employees' economic and moral interests. The objective is to critically analyse the statutory, contractual, and jurisprudential mechanisms governing employee inventions and to recommend reforms that better align employer rights with inventor protections. Using a doctrinal legal methodology grounded in analysis of statutory instruments, OAPI provisions, collective agreements, case law and realities from African Regional Intellectual Property Organization (ARIPO), the study finds that while employers generally hold patent entitlement for employee inventions, employees' rights to remuneration are narrowly defined and often contingent on internal employer policies or court intervention, leaving inventors with limited recourse. A major recommendation is to institute clearer statutory criteria for inventor remuneration, mandatory disclosure obligations, and enforceable compensation standards that reflect the commercial value of employee inventions and reduce reliance on *ad hoc* judicial determinations.

Keywords: Contractual Duty, Patent, Entitlement, Employee, Inventions.

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Résumé

Cet article examine le régime juridique des inventions de salariés au Cameroun à la lumière de l'Annexe I de l'Organisation Africaine de la Propriété Intellectuelle (OAPI), qui attribue en principe les droits de brevet à l'employeur lorsque l'invention est réalisée dans le cadre de l'emploi ou à l'aide des ressources de l'entreprise, sauf disposition contractuelle contraire. Il s'interroge sur la capacité du droit camerounais de la propriété intellectuelle et du travail à concilier les droits des employeurs avec la protection des inventeurs salariés. Fondée sur une analyse doctrinale des textes législatifs, des dispositions de l'OAPI, de la jurisprudence, des conventions collectives et des expériences observées au sein de l'Organisation Régionale Africaine de la Propriété Intellectuelle (ARIPO), l'étude démontre que, si les employeurs bénéficient généralement de la titularité des inventions, les droits des salariés à une rémunération équitable demeurent insuffisamment définis et souvent dépendants des politiques internes des entreprises ou de l'intervention judiciaire. Elle conclut que le cadre juridique actuel ne protège que partiellement les intérêts économiques et moraux des inventeurs salariés et recommande l'adoption de critères légaux clairs en matière de rémunération, d'obligations de divulgation des inventions et de mécanismes de compensation proportionnés à leur valeur économique, afin de renforcer la sécurité juridique, de réduire les litiges et de favoriser l'innovation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Cameroon, the legal protection of employee-generated inventions is governed by the regional patent regime of the *Organisation Africaine de la Propriété Intellectuelle* (OAPI) under the Bangui Agreement. Under this framework, patents for inventions created in the course of employment or with employer resources generally belong to the employer unless otherwise agreed, while inventors can still be entitled to equitable compensation for inventions outside their explicit duties. This dual regime creates complex issues in defining ownership and remuneration at the intersection of employment and intellectual property law.

An invention means an idea that permits a specific problem in the field of technology to be solved in practice.¹ A patent is a title granted for the protection of an invention.² Inventions can take different forms. Product inventions create new tangible products, process inventions introduce new methods of producing results, machine inventions involve mechanical systems performing functions, composition inventions concern new chemical substances or mixtures, and design inventions protect the ornamental appearance of products. Under the Bangui Agreement, a patent title is granted only if the invention is new, involves an inventive step, and is industrially applicable.

While the creator of intellectual property is typically presumed to be its initial owner, under the Revised Bangui Agreement governing OAPI Member States, inventions and designs made in the course of employment or with employer-provided resources will, in the absence of contrary contractual terms, vest in the employer by law. However, this default position can be altered by clear written agreements, and employees may still be entitled to remuneration in specific circumstances; meaning employers cannot assume unfettered ownership of all employee-created intellectual property (IP).³

Without careful contractual safeguards, a business can find itself legally obligated to assign or license certain intellectual property rights to employees, collaborators, clients, or other external parties. Because IP ownership in the context of employment and collaborative work is not always automatically established; disputes over who holds those rights can easily arise and become contentious.⁴

The rising incidence of disputes over IP ownership in the workplace highlights the importance for businesses, whether small or large, to incorporate precise IP ownership, assignment, and remuneration clauses into employment contracts to clarify rights, manage expectations, and mitigate future legal conflicts between employers and employees over the rightful ownership of intellectual assets. This is because development, research, and creative work are most often carried out by employees. A large share, if not

¹ Article 1(1) Annex I of the Bangui Agreement.

² *Ibid*, article 1(1) paragraph 2.

³ Kelese G.N and Ndukong M.N (2022), Ownership Of Intellectual Property Rights In Work Relations Under Oapi: A Brief Survey, *Kampala International University Law Journal*, VOL 4, ISSUE 1, 2022, p.187.

⁴ Boyle J. & Jenkins J. (2014), *Intellectual Property: Law & the Information Society*, Cases & Materials, 1st ed., Center for the Study of the Public Domain, p.231

the majority of intellectual property rights (IPRs), originate within the context of an employment relationship.⁵

Modern international intellectual property law⁶ has set out baseline principles on how IP created by employees should be allocated, and national lawmakers have incorporated these minimum standards into their domestic legal systems to provide clearer rules on ownership and rights in employment-related creations.⁷

Under traditional common-law principles, an employee is generally regarded as the owner of an invention they independently create as long as it truly qualifies as a “free invention” by being developed on their own time and with their own resources, without using the employer’s equipment, facilities, or confidential information.⁸ In this default rule, the employee retains the patent rights to such an invention unless a contract states otherwise. For example, if an engineer working for a tech company designs a novel gadget entirely at home on weekends using only personal tools and materials, and the invention is not tied to the company’s business or research, the engineer would typically own the patent under common law.

Under the hired-to-invent doctrine, an employer can gain rights to inventions made by an employee when the employee was specifically engaged to invent or solve a defined problem as part of their job, or when inventive duties are a core aspect of their employment, creating an implied obligation to assign the invention to the employer,⁹ hired-to-invent case law principles.¹⁰ In these circumstances, even without an express written assignment, courts may treat the employer as entitled to the invention because it was the very task for which the employee was hired. Conversely, if the employee was not hired with an inventive purpose or the invention falls outside the scope of assigned duties, the default common-law rule generally presumes the employee retains ownership, though the employer may still have limited usage rights under doctrines like shop rights.¹¹

It is therefore important to examine employee inventions and commissioned inventions, conduct a comparative analysis of the prevailing legal regimes in ARIPO member states, identify the key legal issues at stake, and propose recommendations for addressing these challenges.

⁵ Chandler P. A., (1992), Employee’s Inventions: Outstanding Compensation, *Journal of Business Law* 600, p.34

⁶ The modern international legal instruments governing patents include the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) (WTO), the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property (WIPO), the Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) (WIPO), and the Patent Law Treaty (PLT) (WIPO).

⁷ Fisk L. Catherine (2009), Working knowledge : employee Innovation and the Rise of Corporate Intellectual Property, University of North Carolina Press, United States of America, p. 1.

⁸ Kantchop T. Noël (2017), Le titre dans l’accord de Bangui, contribution à la systématisation du droit de la propriété intellectuelle dans l’espace OAPI, p.225

⁹ Uzoka, N. C., & Onwugbenu, O. E. (2024). Hired-to-invent: A critical appraisal of employees’ invention, licences and agreements, *Nnamdi Azikiwe University Journal of Human Rights Law*, p.40.

¹⁰ Roisah, K., Utama, Y. J., & Saraswati, R. (2018). Status and contemporary development of employee inventions ownership in G-20 countries, p.214.

¹¹ *Ibid*, p.215.

II. EMPLOYEE INVENTIONS AND COMMISSIONED INVENTIONS

OAPI does not make a substantive legal distinction in ownership principles between employee inventions and commissioned inventions. Both of them all under the same provision assigning rights to employer or commissioner by default, but it provides conditional remuneration rights depending on how the invention was made and its importance.

Article 11 of Annex I of the 2015 Bangui Agreement clearly delineates the pathways through which inventors employed in OAPI Member States such as Cameroon attain or lose entitlement to patent rights, thus constituting the foundational legal framework for analysing employee-invention disputes. At its core, this provision operates on the premise that, in the absence of contractual provisions more favourable to the employee, the general rule of employer entitlement applies to inventions made in the course of employment that incorporate explicit inventive duties or assigned research tasks.¹² Under this scenario, the patent right vests in the employer, yet the law recognises the employee's contribution by mandating additional remuneration that must be agreed by negotiation or, failing that, fixed by competent domestic courts, thereby embedding an element of economic justice into the entitlement regime.¹³

In *Shanks v. Unilever plc & Others*,¹⁴ the United Kingdom Supreme Court held that an employee inventor was entitled to compensation from his employer when the patent granted to the employer had provided an "outstanding benefit" under the UK Patents Act 1977, even though the patent initially belonged to the employer by virtue of the employment relationship. Professor Ian Shanks, who developed a glucose-testing technology while employed by a Unilever subsidiary, successfully claimed that the net benefit of approximately £24 million derived by Unilever from licenses and subsequent sale of patents was sufficiently significant to qualify as outstanding, and the court awarded him a fair share of roughly £2 million as appropriate compensation after considering the benefit in context rather than merely comparing it with Unilever's overall turnover, thus reinforcing that employee inventors can be compensated for inventions that substantially benefit their employers.

The Bangui Agreement adopts a distinct entitlement path for inventions produced by employees not explicitly obliged to invent under their employment contract but who nonetheless uses techniques, means, or information provided by the employer.¹⁵ In such cases, the right to a patent initially belongs to the employee; thereby affirming the inventor's primary claim. Yet the employer retains a qualified right "to be granted the ownership or enjoyment of all or part of the rights attached to the patent". This qualified

¹² Article (1) (a).

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ *Shanks v. Unilever plc & Others* [2019] UKSC 45

¹⁵ Article 11 (1) (b) of Annex I.

entitlement is subject to the employee securing a *fair price* to be negotiated, and in the absence of agreement, fixed by the court with regard to both parties' inputs and the invention's industrial and commercial utility. Such a bifurcation acknowledges that employment may confer access to resources without automatically extinguishing the inventor's entitlement, but it simultaneously recognises the employer's stake in innovations that arise from the business context.

Employees whose job duties involve actual research are generally considered to be hired to create inventions, whereas those who are employed merely to work on development are usually not regarded as being hired to invent. For example, in *Barlow & Seelig Mfg. Co. v. Patch*,¹⁶ a mechanical engineer was instructed to look for ways to enhance a washing machine and ended up inventing a new transmission mechanism that improved his employer's product. When a dispute arose over who owned the patent rights, the Wisconsin Supreme Court sided with the engineer, explaining that his role was not to invent new devices but to improve and develop the existing product the company was producing.

Importantly, article 11 further emphasises procedural duties and safeguards. Employees must immediately notify their employer of any invention¹⁷ and both parties must exchange all pertinent information and refrain from disclosures that could undermine patent rights.¹⁸ By requiring written agreements on employee inventions under pain of nullity¹⁹, the regime seeks to enhance *contractual clarity and certainty*, thereby reducing the scope for disputes. Additionally, the employer's express renunciation of the right to the patent transfers entitlement to the inventor.²⁰ The Bangui Agreement expressly extended to public employees,²¹ illustrating its intent to cover all employment contexts within the OAPI system.²²

In Melin v. United States (1973),²³ a lumber company's general manager was put in charge of overseeing the construction of a new plant and told to include as much labor-saving machinery as possible. In trying to fulfil that task, he came up with a concept for a semi-automatic lumber-handling device and later obtained a patent on it. When ownership of that patent was contested, the court held that the manager himself, not the company, owned the rights to the patent because his job description did not require him to invent new equipment. He was simply expected to supervise and improve efficiency, not to create entirely new inventions. The employer instructed the general manager to focus on installing as much efficiency-enhancing machinery as he could in the new facility, rather than to create any new inventions.

¹⁶ *Barlow & Seelig Manufacturing Co. v. Patch*, 232 Wis. 220, 286 N.W. 577 (Wis. 1939).

¹⁷ *Ibid*, Article 11(2).

¹⁸ *Ibid*, Article 11(3).

¹⁹ *Ibid*, Article 11(4).

²⁰ *Ibid*, Article 11(5).

²¹ This include; employees of the State, public bodies and any other public legal person.

²² Article 11(6).

²³ *Melin v. United States*, 478 F.2d 1210 (U.S. Court of Claims 1973).

Whether an invention created by an employee belongs to the employer depends on the terms of the employment contract and the nature of the working relationship. If an engineer or similar specialist makes an invention as part of the duties they were hired to perform, then it is generally understood that the employer will own the resulting rights because the employee has an implied obligation of loyalty to the employer. This duty means that owning or exploiting the invention personally would conflict with their responsibilities.²⁴ In such situations, even if the employee has obtained a patent in their own name, a court can require that the patent and associated rights be transferred to the employer.

III. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS: CAMEROONIAN/OAPI VS. ARIPO REGIMES

Under the Bangui Agreement Annex I, employee inventions are expressly regulated as part of the patent entitlement regime. Section 11(1)(a) provides that where an employee's contract requires inventive activity, the right to the patent belongs to the employer, and the employee is entitled to supplementary remuneration if the invention is of very exceptional importance, with courts fixing the remuneration in the absence of an agreement. Section 11(1)(b) further stipulates that where no contractual inventive duty exists but the employee uses employer-provided means or information, the patent right initially belongs to the employee. Although the employer may obtain ownership in return for a fair price fixable by the courts, all other inventions belong to the employee. These provisions make employee-invention entitlement a substantive part of the regional patent law itself, creating clear pathways from contractual obligations to patent entitlement and tying remuneration rights to patent ownership.

Section 11's reach is broad: it applies to all employees, including those of public bodies and the State, unless there are specific contrary provisions. The Agreement also mandates notification obligations and the requirement that any agreement on employee inventions be in writing.²⁵ This detailed statutory framework gives uniform and predictable entitlement and remuneration standards in OAPI member states such as Cameroon, reducing reliance on fragmented national patent or labour laws.

By contrast, the ARIPO governed by the Harare Protocol does not contain detailed regional provisions on employee inventions or remuneration. Section 16 of the Protocol provides only the general rule that "the right to an ARIPO patent shall belong to the inventor or his successor in title", but where the inventor is an employee, entitlement is to be determined by the law of the designated Contracting State.²⁶ This means that ARIPO itself does not prescribe specific rules on when an employer rather than the employee

²⁴ Irish V. (2005), *Intellectual Property Rights for Engineers*, 2nd ed., The Institution of Engineering and Technology, London, United Kingdom, p. 12

²⁵ *Ibid*, Article 11(2-4)

²⁶ Section 16(2) of the Harare protocol.

owns the patent or how compensation should be assessed; rather, these issues are left to national law in each ARIPO member state such as Rwanda, Uganda, or Zimbabwe.

For comparative insight, Mozambique's Industrial Property Code²⁷ offers a statutory approach to employee invention entitlement that, in some respects, provides clearer and more detailed remuneration protections than the OAPI Bangui Agreement. Under Mozambique's Code, where an invention is made during the performance of an employment contract involving inventive activity or duties corresponding to research specifically assigned to the employee, the patent right belongs to the employer²⁸ mirroring the employer-entitlement rule found in Section 11(1)(a) of the Bangui Agreement. However, Mozambique's framework goes further in Article 44 by expressly defining "employee" for the purposes of entitlement and by linking remuneration directly to employment conditions. Thus, if an invention falls outside the contract and yet, the employee used employer means, the employer still obtains the patent right but the employee must be "justly compensated."²⁹ This statutory requirement expressly requires compensation without leaving it solely to court discretion. Furthermore, Mozambique's law allows arbitration³⁰ in the absence of agreement on compensation. And if the agreed remuneration is not paid within the agreed timeframe, the employer loses the patent right in favour of the employee.³¹ This sanction is absent in the Bangui Agreement. By contrast, Section 11 of the Bangui Agreement (2015) requires fair price or supplementary remuneration to be fixed by a competent court where parties disagree but does not provide sanction mechanisms such as loss of patent rights for non-payment. This comparative national scheme therefore illustrates that national industrial property laws in some ARIPO member states can offer more robust protective and enforcement measures for inventor compensation than the broader OAPI regional regime, even while both regimes recognise employer entitlement where inventions arise in the course of employment.³²

The result is a fundamental difference in how employee inventions are treated. Under OAPI, detailed entitlement and remuneration provisions are embedded directly in the regional patent law applied uniformly in Cameroon and other OAPI members, offering clearer statutory pathways from employment duties to patent rights and associated compensation. Under ARIPO, by contrast, the lack of specific regional rules means that employee invention entitlement varies by national legislation, potentially creating inconsistency and varying protection for inventors depending on domestic law. In practice, this means that an ARIPO patent applicant must look to the law of the Contracting State to determine whether an employer or employee holds rights and

²⁷Industrial Property Code (approved by Decree No. 47/2015 of 31 December 2015)* (entered into force March 31, 2016). Instituto da Propriedade Industrial.

²⁸ *Ibid*, Article 43.

²⁹ *Ibid*, Article 43(b).

³⁰ *Ibid*, Article 45(2).

³¹ *Ibid*, Article 45(4-5)

³² Article 1(a)–(b) of Annex I.

whether remuneration is statutory, whereas under the OAPI regime, Section 11 of Annex I serves as the primary source of law on these issues.

In a 13 May 2025 decision,³³ the Provincial Court of Barcelona (Section 15), specialising in industrial property, upheld a lower court ruling in a dispute over the ownership of a Spanish patent and utility model relating to a thermal disinfection system, concluding that the patents had been improperly registered by one partner in his own name despite substantial contributions by a technical collaborator and two companies involved in joint development. The court recognised the collaborator as a co-inventor and confirmed the right of the companies to co-ownership of the patent and utility model, stressing that ownership must reflect the actual inventive contributions and that actions to recover ownership protect both inventorship and contractual loyalty in collaborative innovation.

Thus, the Barcelona case illustrates a comparative legal approach to employee-employer invention disputes where patent ownership is determined by actual inventive contribution and contractual context. This concept resonates with how OAPI member states and their courts would interpret patent ownership when employee inventions are contested under contract and patent law principles.

IV. KEY LEGAL ISSUES

Some key legal issues that call for examination turn around the ambiguous classification of inventions, inadequate compensation standards, interpretative uncertainty, the absence of mandatory employer protocols for handling employee invention disclosures undermines transparency and fairness in intellectual property allocation and the moral and economic interests of inventors.

a. Ambiguous classification of inventions

Determining whether an invention was made “in execution of the contract” or merely using employer resources remains subjective. However, the information or resources used by the employees in the course of their contract of employment is qualitative not quantitative. If the employer can prove that the invention was impossible without his resources and information, the employer may claim entitlement to the invention and the corresponding patent rights, subject to any statutory or contractual rights of the employee inventor. Courts and employment agreements play a central role in making this distinction, often leading to unpredictability and litigation.

The 2015 Bangui Agreement provisions create distinct categories of employee inventions, but the legal definitions remain conceptually imprecise, leaving substantial interpretive work to courts and practitioners. Under article 11 of Annex I, inventions

³³ Sentencia Civil 619/2025, Audiencia Provincial Civil nº 15, Rec 92/2024 (13 May 2025) (Spain) ECLI: ES:APB:2025:7775.

arising within a contract that “*comporte une mission inventive*” that is, those that correspond to actual inventive duties or expressly assigned research belong to the employer.³⁴ Whereas inventions made outside assigned duties, but using employer data or means, initially belong to the employee.³⁵ All other inventions belong to the employee.³⁶

Although this tripartite framework ostensibly distinguishes *mission inventions* from *non-mission inventions*, it fails to offer clear criteria for determining which inventions genuinely fall into each category. For example, the phrase “using techniques or means specific to the establishment, or information it has procured” as per sub section 1(b)) leaves open questions as to how much use of resources is sufficient to trigger employer interest and how this should be evidenced in practice. Without clarified thresholds either quantitative or qualitative for resource use or task scope, courts are forced to interpret broadly framed legal terms, which can produce inconsistent outcomes when adjudicating whether the employee’s work stemmed from inherent duties or opportunistic use of workplace resources.

b. Inadequate compensation standards

Under OAPI, employee compensation rights are recognized but lack statutory standards for quantifying remuneration. Employment contracts and judicial discretion fill this vacuum, exposing inventors to unequal bargaining positions and potential under-compensation.

Although Annex I recognises that employees should be compensated for inventions made outside their contractual duties, the provisions lack objective criteria for determining the *quantum* of compensation or defining how commercial and industrial utility should weigh into remuneration calculations. Section 11(1)(b) requires that where the employer seeks ownership of rights attached to a patent originally belonging to the employee, the employee shall receive *un juste prix*.³⁷ However, in the absence of an agreement, this price is fixed by the competent domestic court based on available information concerning contributions and use. While this language suggests a judicial safety net, it provides no statutory yardstick for courts to assess what constitutes a just price or fair price or how to balance employer investment against inventor contribution.

The complexity of valuing inventions especially those with potential high future commercial value underscores the inadequacy of a provision that turns wholly on judicial discretion without guidelines on industrial valuation or formulaic assessment. Coupled with the fact that remuneration for inventions falling under sub section 1(a) is only triggered when very exceptional importance is shown. In consequence, employee inventors may find themselves disadvantaged unless they negotiate more favorable contractual terms. An advantageous bargaining position for employees is often elusive in the absence of collective labour strength or specialist legal advice.

³⁴*Ibid*, Article 11 (1) (a).

³⁵ *Ibid*, Article 11 (1) (b).

³⁶ *Ibid*, Article 11 (1) (c).

³⁷ This means a fair price.

c. Interpretative uncertainty

Despite the efforts of the Bangui Agreement to regulate the ownership of employee inventions, significant interpretative and practical challenges remain. Annex I establishes a framework for distinguishing between inventions made in the execution of an employment contract, inventions made outside contractual duties, and independent inventions.³⁸ However, the provision does not define several key concepts upon which ownership and remuneration depend. Terms such as “in execution of the contract” and “use of employer means or information” are left largely undefined, creating uncertainty regarding the proper classification of inventions. As a result, determining whether an invention belongs to the employer or the employee often depends on the specific circumstances of each case and, ultimately, on judicial interpretation.

This lack of precision may lead to inconsistent outcomes and undermine legal certainty for both employers and employees. Employees may be uncertain about the extent of their proprietary rights, while employers may face difficulties in assessing the scope of their entitlement to inventions developed by their workforce.³⁹

A further challenge concerns the remuneration of employee inventors. While the Bangui Agreement recognises the possibility of compensation in certain circumstances, it provides little guidance on the criteria for determining the amount of remuneration owed. Consequently, compensation often depends on contractual arrangements, internal employer policies, or judicial discretion. This approach may produce unequal outcomes and may fail to adequately reflect the commercial value of an invention or the inventor’s contribution to its development.⁴⁰

Comparative experiences from other jurisdictions demonstrate that clearer legislative and regulatory frameworks can improve predictability and fairness. Jurisdictions that provide statutory definitions, remuneration guidelines, and procedural obligations for disclosure and negotiation offer greater protection to inventors while preserving employers’ legitimate interests in innovations developed within the employment relationship. Such measures promote transparency, reduce disputes, and facilitate the efficient exploitation of intellectual property.

Accordingly, there is a strong case for reforming the Bangui patent framework and its implementing regulations to provide clearer interpretative standards, objective remuneration criteria, and structured procedures for handling employee inventions. Such reforms would strengthen legal certainty, ensure more consistent application of the law, and achieve a more equitable balance between employer entitlement and inventor protection.

³⁸ Article 11 .

³⁹ The absence of clear statutory guidance also increases the likelihood of disputes and litigation, particularly where inventions are developed outside normal working hours but are connected in some way to the employer’s activities, resources, or confidential information.

⁴⁰ The absence of objective standards also weakens the bargaining position of employees, particularly where there is a significant imbalance of power between employer and employee.

d. The absence of mandatory employer protocols for handling employee invention disclosures undermines transparency and fairness in intellectual property allocation

From a critical perspective, the lack of legally mandated, standardized procedures requiring employers to promptly acknowledge and negotiate employee invention disclosures creates a significant imbalance in innovation-driven workplaces. Although provisions such as article 11(2)–(3) may implicitly suggest duties of notification and information-sharing, their non-operational nature allows employers wide discretion in how or even whether they engage with employee inventors. This regulatory gap can lead to delayed responses, informal or opaque decision-making, and weakened bargaining positions for employees who often lack access to legal or institutional support.

As a result, disputes over ownership and remuneration are frequently escalated to litigation only after trust has broken down and evidence trails have become harder to establish. The absence of clear timelines and enforceable procedural obligations therefore not only undermines transparency but also discourages early settlement of rights, ultimately weakening both employee confidence in the system and the efficiency of intellectual property governance in innovation-intensive sectors.

e. Moral and economic interests of inventors

Although employees may legally be entitled to remuneration and recognition as inventors, practical enforcement often depends on litigation, which may be costly and time-consuming, thereby discouraging individual inventors. The capacity of an ordinary employee to go against an employer is disproportionate as a result of lack of resources to prove ownership. The Bangui Agreement's provisions nominally balance employer control with employee moral and economic interests, but in practice the employee's position remains relatively weak. The legal text confirms that an employee must immediately inform the employer and share all useful information regarding the invention⁴¹, and that any agreement must be in writing,⁴² thereby reinforcing procedural obligations and transparency. These obligations recognise the inventor's continuing stake in the invention process.

Nevertheless, employers may acquire all or part of the rights associated with an invention developed outside the employee's contractual duties under subsection 1(b), notwithstanding the employee's initial ownership of the invention. This exception shifts the balance of power in favour of the employer and limits the practical significance of the employee's proprietary rights. Without transparent valuation methods and enforceable compensation mechanisms, employee inventors risk receiving remuneration that does not reflect the true commercial value of their inventions. Furthermore, compensation frameworks that hinge on judicial determination in the absence of prior agreement risk undervaluing the inventor's contribution or deterring employees from asserting their rights due to the costs, time, and uncertainty of litigation. This systemic imbalance can

⁴¹ Sub section 2-3.

⁴² *Ibid*, section 4.

weaken incentives for innovation by individual inventors within the employment context, particularly in environments where institutional support for inventors is limited and contractual terms tend to favour employers.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

To address the ambiguities in the classification of inventions, the Cameroon legislator in this case the Bangui Legislator should consider incorporating into the regulations for the implementation of the Bangui agreement⁴³ and the administrative instructions,⁴⁴ clearly defined key terms used in Section 11 of Annex I such as “in execution of the contract” and “use of employer means or information”. Clear statutory definitions and illustrative criteria would help to reduce interpretive uncertainty and reliance on judicial discretion when distinguishing between inventions of mission, non-mission inventions, and independent innovations. Such clarification would align entitlement rules with predictable legal standards, minimise litigation, and improve legal certainty for inventors and employers alike.

Given the gaps in remuneration standards under the Bangui Agreement, Cameroon or the Bangui legislator should adopt statutory remuneration benchmarks or formulaic guidelines, similar to those found in other jurisdictions like China where employee inventor compensation is tied to quantifiable metrics such as percentages of operating profit or licensing income in the absence of agreement.⁴⁵ This guide however must be used and appreciated by the courts to determine the amount of compensation. Establishing objective factors for example, contribution weighting, profit share, or fixed minimum percentages will help domestic courts and negotiating parties arrive at fair outcomes more consistently, reduce arbitrariness in awards, and better protect the economic interests of inventors.

To ensure timely and transparent handling of employee inventions, national law should mandate that employers establish formal reporting and negotiation protocols for inventions disclosed by employees. Such protocols could require employers to acknowledge receipt of invention disclosures within defined timelines, initiate good-faith negotiations on remuneration terms, and provide reasoned written responses to inventors. This would operationalize the notification and information-sharing obligations

⁴³ The implementing regulations for the Bangui Agreement (Act of 14 December 2015) were adopted by the Administrative Council of the Organisation Africaine de la Propriété Intellectuelle (OAPI through Resolution No. 60/29 on 8 December 2020. This resolution formally adopted the Règlement d'application de l'Accord de Bangui, Acte du 14 décembre 2015, providing the detailed procedural and administrative rules needed to implement the substantive provisions of the revised Agreement, including the provisions on patents and employee inventions.

⁴⁴ OAPI, Instruction Administrative n° 11.03, adopted and signed on 21 December 2021, with entry into force on 1 January 2022 for the implementation of the Bangui Agreement and the associated annexes when they come into force.

⁴⁵ Design Patent Applications - New Rules in Third Revision of the "Implementing Regulations of the Patent Law of the People's Republic of China" 2024-03-27

already implied in Section 11(2)–(3) and reduce disputes by promoting early resolution rather than reliance on post-hoc court determinations.

Because employee-invention disputes often hinge on nuanced assessments of contractual obligations, contribution levels, and economic value, Cameroon should invest in capacity building for judges and tribunal members who handle IP-labour interface cases. Training on patent valuation,⁴⁶ comparative compensation standards, and the doctrinal intents of Section 11 would help ensure that judicial determinations are consistent, predictable, and informed by best practices in employee-invention law. This step would enhance not just the quality of adjudication, but also the overall credibility of the entitlement regime within the domestic legal system.

VI. CONCLUSION

Cameroon's OAPI-based patent regime offers a structured approach to the protection of inventions and includes mechanisms intended to balance corporate ownership with inventor interests. However, persistent ambiguity and limited statutory guidance on employee remuneration highlight the need for reform. Moreover, comparison with ARIPO systems illustrates that regional harmonization offers advantages in certainty and administration, but the underlying employee-invention rights often ultimately depend on national laws. Improving legislative clarity and compensation standards will enhance innovation incentives and strengthen legal protections for employee inventors across diverse African patent regimes.

⁴⁶Adamu S and Ntara W. A., (2024), Legal Analysis of the Pledge of Patents in Cameroon: Navigating Through the Technicalities of the Use of Patents as Collateral Securities, *Revue de la Recherche Juridique et Politique – RRJP Review of Law and Political Research* – RLPR Vol. 2 Iss. 9 p. 94.